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доктор медицинских наук, профессор Ташкентского государственного стоматологического института **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-9235-1742

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2.	Alimova Dono Mirjamolovna, Mustagizova Feruza Abduraximovna THE ROLE OF PERIODONTAL DISEASE IN CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASE.....	18
3.	Amonov Shavkat Ergashevich, Bezbakh Dmitry Ilyich, Amonov Aminjon Shavkatovich LARYNGEAL PAPILOMATOSIS: A REVIEW OF MODERN METHODS OF DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT.....	25
4.	Nuraliyev Nekkadam Abdullayevich, Razikova Dilnoza Kadyrovna INDICATIONS OF IMMUNE SYSTEM HUMORAL IMMUNE FACTORS IN RELAPSING HERPETIC STOMATITIS IN CHILDREN.....	31
5.	Eshimova Parvina Behzod qizi, Alimova Dono Mirjamalovna, Suleymenov Askar Nurlanovich A MODERN PERSPECTIVE ON LOCAL TREATMENT OF RECURRENT APHTHOUS STOMATITIS.....	36
6.	Kuryazov Shoxrux Akbarovich METHODS OF EARLY DIAGNOSIS OF ORAL ORGAN PATHOLOGIES IN GIRLS DURING PUBERTY.....	41
7.	Suleymenov Askar Nurlanovich, Alimova Dono Mirjamalovna, Eshimova Parvina Behzod qizi COMPARISON OF THE CLINICAL AND RADIOLOGICAL EFFICACY OF EPOXY SILERS OF TRADITIONAL COMPOSITION AND WITH ADDITIVES OF QUATERNARY AMMONIUM.....	50

ONCOLOGY

8.	Djanklich Sayde Mustafayevna, Tillyashaykhov Mirzagaleb Nigmatovich, Imamov Olim Abdilhodjayevich, Berkinov Alisher Aliyevich, Ismailova Umida Abdullayevna PREVALENCE OF CERVICAL CANCER IN UZBEKISTAN: INCIDENCE AND MORTALITY.....	56
9.	Iskandarova Shakhnoza Tulkinovna, Khakimova Laylo Nuraliyevna, Yusupov Anvar Sobirovich SPECIFIC FEATURES OF ORGANIZING THE ANESTHESIOLOGY SERVICE IN AN ONCOLOGICAL CLINIC DURING MAJOR UPPER ABDOMINAL SURGERY.....	66
10.	Islamov Khurshid Jamshidovich ANALYSIS OF TREATMENT RESULTS FOR PATIENTS WITH RECTAL METASTIC CANCER.....	75
11.	Malikov Muzaffar Abduvakhobovich DEVELOPMENT OF A DIAGNOSTIC AND TREATMENT ALGORITHM FOR DIFFERENTIATED THYROID CANCER BASED ON THE APPLICATION OF MOLECULAR-GENETIC ANALYSIS METHODS.....	83
12.	Sapura Ibragimova, Klevleeva Albina, Babakhanova Nargiza, Rizayeva Feruza, Erimbetova Indira, Nigmatov Khamidhon, Aripova Nazokat OUTCOMES OF BLINATUMOMAB THE INITIAL PHASE OF CHEMOTHERAPY IN CHILDREN WITH B-CELL ALL.....	91
13.	Raximov Nodir Maxammatkulovich, Shaxanova Shaxnoza Shavkatovna, Assatulaev Akmal Farxadovich, Khakimov Alisher Abduraxmonovich COMPREHENSIVE RISK ASSESSMENT OF THROMBOCYTOPENIA IN ONCOLOGY PATIENTS: FROM PREDICTORS TO PERSONALIZED THERAPY.....	97

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THE ROLE OF HBV RNA IN THE EARLY DIAGNOSIS OF HBV-ASSOCIATED HEPATOCELLULAR CARCINOMA.....107
15. **Tillyashayxov Mirzagaleb Nigmatovich, Malikov Muzaffar Abduvakhobovich**
EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF COMBINED TREATMENT OF DIFFERENTIATED THYROID CANCER.....112
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MODERN CONCEPTS OF PATHOGENESIS AND MORPHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF HPV-ASSOCIATED LESIONS OF THE VULVA AND CERVIX.....119

HEALTHCARE

17. **Israilova Gulida Maratovna, Tuxtarov Baxrom Eshnazarovich, Kodirov Dilmurod Alimxon O'g'li**
METHODS FOR ENHANCING THE TECHNOLOGY OF FORTIFYING FUNCTIONAL MEAT PRODUCTS IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN.....124
18. **Nasirova Rano Rakhimovna**
ELECTRONIC MEDICAL RECORDS IN MILITARY MEDICINE: MODERN CAPABILITIES AND IMPLEMENTATION PROSPECTS.....132

INTERNAL DISEASES

19. **Aripdjanova Shakhlo Sardarovna, Zufarov Pulat Saatovich, Baykhanova Dilrabo Jamalitdinovna, Ashurova Munisa Jalalitinovna**
USE OF ADAPTOGENS IN THE COMPLEX THERAPY OF PATIENTS WITH CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASES.....142
20. **Mamasoliyev Nematjon Soliyevich, Nishonova Nodiraxon Akramovna, Botirov Jaxongir Akramjon Ug'li**
CHARACTERISTICS OF THE DEVELOPMENT AND CHANGE OF PRENOSOLOGICAL RISK FACTORS OF ARTERIAL HYPOTENSION IN THE CONDITIONS OF THE ANDIJAN REGION (PROMISING ANALYSIS OF THE STUDY).....146
21. **Mamasoliyev Nematjon Soliyevich, Nishonova Nodiraxon Akramovna, Botirov Jaxongir Akramjon Ug'li**
LONG-TERM FEATURES OF THE FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF AGE-RELATED FACTORS OF SMOKING, ALCOHOL CONSUMPTION, AND HYPERCHOLESTEROLEMIA IN THE VALLEY, DEPENDING ON THE PREMORBID PREVENTION OF ARTERIAL HYPOTENSION.....152
22. **Zufarov Pulat Saatovich, Aripdjanova Shakhlo Sardarovna, Baikhanova Dilrabo Jamalitdinovna, Ashurova Munisa Jalalitinovna**
USE OF ADAPTOGENS IN THE COMPLEX THERAPY OF PATIENTS WITH CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASES.....157

PEDIATRIC SURGERY AND PEDIATRICS

23. **Ibragimov Qurbonmurod Niyozovich, Akhmedov Yusufjon Maxmudovich**
EVALUATION OF THE RESULTS OF POSTOPERATIVE COMPLICATIONS IN THE SCROTAL FORM OF HYPOSPADIAS IN CHILDREN.....162

24. **Hasanov Aziz Batir O'g'li, Yusupov Shuxrat Abduqosim O'g'li**
MORPHOLOGICAL AND MORPHOMETRIC CHARACTERISTICS OF BONE TISSUE IN ALLOXAN-INDUCED OSTEOPATHY AND ITS CORRECTION.....167
25. **Muxamedjanova Fatima Rustamovna**
COMPARATIVE ASSESSMENT OF ANTHROPOMETRIC AND SOMATIC INDICATORS IN CHILDREN PLAYING CHESS AND STUDYING ACCORDING TO THE GENERAL EDUCATION PROGRAM.....173
26. **Muxamedjanova Fatima Rustamovna**
FEATURES OF THE PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT OF CHILDREN WHO PLAY CHESS.....181
27. **Rakhmatullaev Akmal Abadbekovich, Terebaev Bilim Aldamuratovich, Abdullaev Kuddus Eshkurbanovich**
CURRENT ISSUES OF DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF PRIMARY OBSTRUCTIVE MEGAURETER IN CHILDREN.....186
28. **Kurbonov Djafar Djurakulovich, Azizov Mamatkul Kurbanovich, Khurramov Farrukh Mukhsinovich**
COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF TREATMENT OUTCOMES FOR VARIOUS FORMS OF ACUTE ABDOMINAL PATHOLOGY IN CHILDREN.....197

MORPHOLOGY

29. **Ruziev Sherzod Ibadullayevich., Ismailova Mexriban Olimbayevna**
FORENSIC SIGNIFICANCE OF VASCULAR PLEXUS AND VENTRICULAR MORPHOLOGY IN TRAUMATIC BRAIN INJURIES.....207
30. **Ruziev Sherzod Ibadullayevich., Ismailova Mexriban Olimbayevna**
METHODS OF STUDYING THE VASCULAR PLEXUS AND VENTRICULAR SYSTEM IN TRAUMATIC BRAIN INJURIES.....215
31. **Sapaeva Sharofat Aminovna**
MORPHOSTRUCTURAL CHANGES IN LUNG TISSUE IN AN EXPERIMENTAL MODEL OF SURFACTANT DEFICIENCY.....221
32. **Ulugbekova Gulrukh Juraevna, Adkhamov Shokhjakhon Abdullajon Ugli**
AGE- AND GENDER-SPECIFIC MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN CRANIOMETRICAL INDICATORS OF THE HEAD AND CRANIAL INDEX IN CHILDREN OF EARLY SCHOOL AGE.....228

NEUROLOGY AND PSYCHIATRY

33. **Adambaev Zufar Ibragimovich, Kilichev Ibodulla Abdullaevich, Saparbaev Kudrat Ismailovich**
TREATMENT OF ISCHEMIC STROKE: FOCUS ON NEUROREGENERATION - MODERN STRATEGIES AND PROSPECTS.....233
34. **Dusov Abdimurod Kholmurodovich, Ochilov Ulugbek Usmanovich, Dusov Tursunmurad Kholmurodovich**
COMPREHENSIVE ASSESSMENT OF DELAYED HELP-SEEKING FOR PSYCHIATRIC CARE: AN ANALYSIS BASED ON AN INDEXING METHOD.....245
35. **Dusov Abdimurod Kholmurodovich, Ochilov Ulugbek Usmanovich, Dusov Tursunmurad Kholmurodovich**
FORMS AND SEVERITY LEVELS OF EMOTIONAL-VOLITIONAL DEFICIT IN PARANOID SCHIZOPHRENIA AND THEIR CLINICAL-DYNAMIC CHARACTERISTICS.....252

36. **Ismailov Zakhidjon, Mirdjuraev Elbek**
DIAGNOSIS, TREATMENT AND COMPREHENSIVE REHABILITATION OF CHILDREN WITH DISEASES OF THE PERIPHERAL NERVOUS SYSTEM.....262
37. **Ismailov Zakhidjon, Mirdjuraev Elbek**
RESULTS OF COMPREHENSIVE REHABILITATION OF CHILDREN WITH DISEASES OF THE PERIPHERAL NERVOUS SYSTEM.....275
38. **Madjidova Yakuthon Nabiyevna, Ergasheva Nargiza Nasriddinovna, Hasanova Nafisa Okilovna**
ASSESSMENT OF THE FUNCTIONAL STATE OF THE MUSCULOSKELETAL SYSTEM IN CHILDREN WITH CEREBRAL PALSY.....284
39. **Mirdjuraev Elbek, Ismailov Zakhidjon**
OPTIMIZATION OF REHABILITATION OF CHILDREN WITH DISEASES OF THE NEUROMOTOR SYSTEM.....290
40. **Mirjurayev Elbek Mirshavkatovich, Adambayev Zufar Ibragimovich, Samiyev Asliddin Sayitovich, Ergashev G'ulom Bo'riyevich**
REHABILITATION OF NON-SPECIFIC BACK PAIN CAUSED BY MODIC SPONDYLODISCITIS: A RANDOMIZED CONTROLLED TRIAL.....299
41. **Ruzmetova Saodat Umarjonovna**
PERINATAL INVOLVEMENT OF CENTRAL NERVOUS SYSTEM AND ITS IMPACT ON CHILD DEVELOPMENT.....306
42. **Samiyev Asliddin Sayitovich, Bobomurodov Gayrat Allamurodovich, Khushvaktov Nizom Zoirovich, Samiyev Bobur Asliddinovich**
EFFECTIVENESS OF COMPLEX TREATMENT FOR PATIENTS WITH MYASTHENIC CRISIS.....312

TRAUMATOLOGY AND ORTHOPEDICS

43. **Axtamov A'zam, Axtamov Azim**
STUDYING THE RESULTS OF RECONSTRUCTIVE SURGICAL TREATMENT OF COMBINED MENISCLE WOUNDS.....316
44. **Axtamov A'zam, Axtamov Azim**
EXPERIENCE IN TREATING INTRA-ARTICULAR FRACTURES OF THE DISTAL PART OF THE HUMERUS IN CHILDREN.....321
45. **Axtamov Azim, Axtamov A'zam**
DIAGNOSIS AND MODERN METHODS OF TREATMENT OF ACETABULUM INJURIES (LITERATURE REVIEW).....325
46. **Urinbayev Payzilla Urinbayevich, Eranov Sherzod Nuraliyevich**
REHABILITATION OF PATIENTS WITH ELBOW JOINT CONTRACTURE IN IMPROPERLY UNIONED SUPRACONDYL FRACTURES OF THE HUMERUS.....332
47. **Zolotova Natalya Nikolaevna**
THE MAIN DIAGNOSTIC AND TREATMENT CRITERIA FOR HIP DISPLASIA IN CHILDREN.....341

SURGERY

48. **Davlatov Salim Sulaymonovich, Khamidov Obid Abdurakhmanovich, Nurmurzayev Zafar Narbayevich**
COMPARATIVE ASSESSMENT OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF MINIMALLY INVASIVE AND TRADITIONAL BILIARY DECOMPRESSION METHODS IN THE COMPREHENSIVE TREATMENT OF BENIGN MECHANICAL JAUNDICE.....344

49. **Eshkabilov Shukurali Davlatmuratovich, Ixtiyorov Talat Vaxobovich**
ENDOSCOPIC BALLOON DILATION OF ANASTOMOTIC STRICTURES AFTER
SURGICAL REPAIR OF ESOPHAGEAL ATRESIA.....355
50. **Khashimov Rustam Uktamjanovich, Rizaev Jasur Alimjanovich, Rakhmanov Kosim
Erdanovich.**
CLINICAL EFFICACY OF MODIFIED AND ENDOVIDEOSURGICAL METHODS IN
HERNIOPLASTY OF INGUINAL HERNIAS.....361
51. **Matlubov Mansur Muratovich, Yusupov Jasur Tolibovich, Khamdamova Eleanora
Gafarovna, Khamdamov Olim Dilmurodovich**
THE ROLE OF ULINASTATIN IN COMPREHENSIVE THERAPY FOR THE
PREVENTION OF POSTOPERATIVE COMPLICATIONS IN CORONARY ARTERY
BYPASS GRAFTING.....371
52. **Rakhimov Oybek Umarovich, Khamdamov Bakhtiyor Zarifovich, Dadayev Shirin
Amanovich**
PERSONALIZED ALGORITHM FOR IMMUNOCORRECTION IN PATIENTS WITH
GENERALIZED PERITONITIS AND HIGH IMMUNOLOGICAL RISK.....378
53. **Togayev Sherkobul Baykobulovich, Baymakov Sayfiddin Risbaevich, Hasanov Bobur
Abduganievich, Ashurov Abdurashid Abdullaevich**
METHODS OF DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF CROHN'S DISEASE OF THE
SMALL AND LARGE INTESTINE.....385

ENDOCRINOLOGY

54. **Alieva Anna Valerovna, Salikhova Zebo Abdulzokhid Kizi, Ismoilova Nazokat
Egamberdi Kizi, Nazarova Bakhora Uktamovna**
COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF WOLFRAM AND ALSTROM SYNDROMES.....390
55. **Alidjanova Durдона Abdullajonovna**
DISORDERS OF MENTAL ACTIVITY IN CHILDREN AND ADOLESCENTS WITH
TYPE 1 DIABETES.....397
56. **Alikhanova Nodira Mirshavkatovna, Isamukhamedova Istiora Sandjarovna,
Abboskhugaeva Lola Saydganiodgaevna**
GLYCEMIC INDEX AND GLYCEMIC LOAD OF FOOD PRODUCTS FOR CLINICAL
PURPOSES IN PATIENTS WITH DIABETES.....408
57. **Akhmedjanova Saodat Fakhadovna**
FUNCTIONAL HYPOTHALAMIC AMENORRHEA: CURRENT INSIGHTS INTO
PATHOGENESIS, DIAGNOSIS, AND THERAPY.....419

OPHTHALMOLOGY

58. **Islamov Ziyovuddin Sadriddinovich, Khamroyeva Yulduz Abdurashidovna, Azimov
Abdullo Asliddin Ugli**
DIAGNOSTIC VALUE OF ELASTOSONOGRAPHY IN CHOROIDDAL TUMORS.....423
59. **Myakushkina Ruslana Rashidovna, Yusupov Azamat Farkhadovich, Karimova
Muyassar Khamitovna, Muxanov Shavkat Abduvaliyevich, Gelmanova Tatyana
Ivanovna**
CHANGES IN ABERRATIONS AND THEIR IMPACT ON VISION AFTER LASIK....429
60. **Tosphulatova Arofat Ziyavutdinovna, Khamraeva Yuvalla-Makhliyo Ulmasalievna**
ORTHOKERATOLOGY LENSES IN THE CONTROL OF MYOPIA PROGRESSION IN
CHILDREN (REVIEW ARTICLE).....434
61. **Turakulova Dilfuza Mukhitdinovna, Nazirova Zulfiya Rustamovna, Yunusova Komila
Bakhodirovna**
THE ROLE OF TONOGRAPHIC INDICATORS OF THE EYE IN THE CARE OF
CHILDREN WITH CONGENITAL GLAUCOMA.....443

БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ БИОМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ | JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

ISMAILOV Zakhidjon
MIRDJURAEV Elbek

Center for the development of professional qualification of medical workers, Tashkent

RESULTS OF COMPREHENSIVE REHABILITATION OF CHILDREN WITH DISEASES OF THE PERIPHERAL NERVOUS SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

Objective: The study was carried out with the aim of improving the condition of patients after treatment and normalizing their usual life activities. Complex rehabilitation measures with the use of medications, including the drug Ipigrix, lead to the preservation of treatment results and the prevention of recurrence of the disease. Of particular importance is the correct choice of diagnostic tactics, treatment and comprehensive rehabilitation of children with diseases of the peripheral nervous system. **Methods:** To improve the diagnostic algorithm, we examined 100 children with various mononeuropathies aged 3 to 18 years. Out of 100 studied children, 80 are children with neuropathy after the use of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (injections), 10 are healthy children caused by excessive use of orthopedic bandages, 10 are patients with neuropathy of various etiologies. Collection of anamnesis allowed us to determine the duration of the disease, the effectiveness of the treatment and the accompanying pathology. Clinical and neurological examinations aimed at identifying sensory, motor, reflex and trophic disorders of patients were carried out. The complex rehabilitation period was 45 days. It used restitution, regeneration, compensation methods of rehabilitation.

Results: The data obtained during the study confirmed the therapeutic significance of the practical application of complex rehabilitation measures developed by us for diseases of the peripheral nervous system in children. **Conclusion:** The use of the complex rehabilitation method we have developed in applied medicine (45 days) allows to significantly improve the clinical course of diseases of the peripheral system, including post-injection mononeuropathy, as well as restore the physical activity of the child, which leads to an improvement in the quality of life.

Key words: peripheral nervous system, ultrasound, diagnostics, rehabilitation, massage, mononeuropathy, children, muscles, skeleton

Исмаилов Захиджон
Мирджураев Эльбек

Центр развития профессиональной квалификации
медицинских работников, Ташкент

РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ КОМПЛЕКСНОЙ РЕАБИЛИТАЦИИ ДЕТЕЙ С ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЯМИ ПЕРИФЕРИЧЕСКОЙ НЕРВНОЙ СИСТЕМЫ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Цель исследования: Исследование было проведено с целью улучшения состояния пациентов после лечения и нормализации их обычной жизнедеятельности. Комплексные реабилитационные мероприятия с применением медикаментозных средств, включая препарат Ипигрикс, способствуют сохранению результатов лечения и предотвращению рецидивов заболевания. Особое значение имеет правильный выбор диагностической тактики, лечения и комплексной реабилитации детей с заболеваниями периферической нервной системы.

Методы: С целью совершенствования алгоритма диагностики нами было обследовано 100 детей с различными мононейропатиями в возрасте от 3 до 18 лет. Из 100 обследованных детей 80 составили дети с нейропатией после применения нестероидных противовоспалительных препаратов (инъекций), 10 – здоровые дети с нарушениями, вызванными чрезмерным использованием ортопедических бандажей, 10 – пациенты с нейропатией различной этиологии. Сбор анамнеза позволил определить длительность заболевания, эффективность проводимого лечения и сопутствующую патологию. Проводились клиничко-неврологические обследования, направленные на выявление нарушений чувствительности, движений, рефлексов и трофических расстройств у пациентов. Период комплексной реабилитации составил 45 дней. Использовались реституционные, регенерационные и компенсаторные методы реабилитации. **Результаты:** Полученные в ходе исследования данные подтвердили терапевтическую значимость практического применения разработанных нами комплексных реабилитационных мероприятий при заболеваниях периферической нервной системы у детей.

Заключение: Применение разработанного нами метода комплексной реабилитации в прикладной медицине (45 дней) позволяет значительно улучшить клиническое течение заболеваний периферической нервной системы, включая постинъекционную мононейропатию, а также восстановить физическую активность ребенка, что приводит к улучшению качества жизни.

Ключевые слова: периферическая нервная система, ультразвуковое исследование, диагностика, реабилитация, массаж, мононейропатия, дети, мышцы, скелет

Исмоилов Захиджон

Мирджўраев Элбек

Тиббиёт ходимларининг касбий малакасини
ривожлантириш маркази, Тошкент

ПЕРИФЕРИК НЕРВ ТИЗИМИ КАСАЛЛИКЛАРИ БИЛАН ОҒРИГАН БОЛАЛАРНИ КОМПЛЕКС РЕАБИЛИТАЦИЯ ҚИЛИШ НАТИЖАЛАРИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Тадқиқот мақсади: Тадқиқот беморларнинг даволашдан кейинги ҳолатини яхшилаш ва уларнинг одатий ҳаётий фаолиятини меъёрлаштириш мақсадида амалга оширилди. Ипигрикс препаратини ўз ичига олган дори воситалари билан комплекс реабилитация тадбирлари даволаш натижаларини сақлаб қолишга ва касалликнинг қайталанишининг олдини олишга ёрдам беради. Периферик нерв тизими касалликлари билан оғриган болаларни ташхислаш тактикаси, даволаш ва комплекс реабилитация қилишни тўғри танлаш алоҳида аҳамиятга эга. **Усуллар:** Ташхислаш алгоритмининг такомиллаштириш мақсадида биз 3 ёшдан 18 ёшгача бўлган турли хил мононейропатияли 100 та болани текширдик. Текширилган 100 та болалардан 80 таси нестероид яллиғланишга қарши дори воситалари (инъекциялар) қўлланилгандан кейин нейропатияси бўлган болалар, 10 таси ортопедик бандажларнинг хаддан ташқари ишлатилиши натижасида бузилишлар юзага келган соғлом болалар, 10 таси турли этиологияли нейропатия билан оғриган беморлар ташкил этди. Анамнез йиғиш касаллик

давомийлиги, ўтказилаётган даволашнинг самарадорлиги ва ҳамроҳ патологияни аниқлашга имкон берди. Беморларда сезувчанлик, ҳаракат, рефлекс ва трофик бузилишларни аниқлашга қаратилган клиник-неврологик текширувлар ўтказилди. Комплекс реабилитация даври 45 кунни ташкил этди. Реституцион, регенерацион ва компенсатор реабилитация усуллари қўлланилди. **Натижалар:** Тадқиқот давомида олинган маълумотлар биз ишлаб чиққан комплекс реабилитация тадбирларини болаларда периферик нерв тизими касалликларида амалий қўллашнинг терапевтик аҳамиятини тасдиқлади. **Хулоса:** Биз ишлаб чиққан комплекс реабилитация усулини амалий тиббиётда қўллаш (45 кун) периферик нерв тизими касалликларининг, шу жумладан инъекциядан кейинги мононейропатиянинг клиник кечишини сезиларли даражада яхшилашга, шунингдек боланинг жисмоний фаоллигини тиклашга имкон беради, бу эса ҳаёт сифатини яхшилашга олиб келади.

Калит сўзлар: периферик нерв тизими, ультратовуш текшируви, ташхислаш, реабилитация, массаж, мононейропатия, болалар, мушаклар, скелет

1. Introduction

In the case of neuropathy, movement disorders are manifested in the development of paresis or paralysis. Neuropathy is accompanied by muscle atrophy, loss of pay reflexes, decreased muscle tone, trophic changes, impaired skin sensation, pain during muscle contraction [1, 2]. Exercise, massage and physiotherapy play an important role in the complex treatment of patients in this group. The purpose of complex rehabilitation treatment for peripheral paralysis is as follows:

- stimulating the renewal and re-excitation of nervous fields in the state of tension;
- prevention of injuries and improvement of vascular condition and trophic processes for this purpose;
- strengthening paretic muscles and buttocks;
- prevent contractures and prevent joint immobility;
- restoration of the labor force through the normalization of movement functions and the development of compensation tools [3]

Exercise therapy is used to relieve pain and relieve the patient's condition. The method and nature of rehabilitation measures are determined by movement disorders, their location and stage of the disease.

Early recovery (2-20 days), late recovery (20-60 days) and residual period (more than 2 months) are distinguished. With surgical intervention on the nerves, the duration of all periods is prolonged and Residual: the period of early recovery can last up to 30-40 days, 3-4 months in the evening and up to 2-3 years in the residential [4, 5].

With the development of paralysis of the wound, optimal conditions are created for the restoration of its functions, treatment with massage and physiotherapy. A distinctive feature of massage for peripheral paralysis is its effect on the muscles, strict dosage, segmental-reflex nature of its effect. (neck area, lumbosacral area massage). Massage has a positive effect on the use of droplet and spiral underwater massage, which combines the massage (vibration) of the apparatus performed at the "action points" and along the paretic muscles, the positive temperature effect of hot water and its mechanical effect on tissues. In the absence of motor functions, electrophoresis with calcium ions is used to increase the permeability of the nerves [6]. After physiotherapeutic methods, therapeutic exercises are performed, which consist of passive and idiomotor exercises for complete paralysis. It is recommended to combine passive exercises with active movements on the same pieces of the symmetrical joint. Special attention should be paid to observing the appearance of voluntary movements during training times, choosing optimal starting positions and supporting the development of active movements [7].

During the evening recovery period, treatment is carried out according to the condition of the patient, massage, healing physical education and physiotherapy are used. The nature of the treatment is determined by the dosage and the depth of the paresis. The deeper the lesion, the longer the treatment lasts (except for active action). During the evening recovery period, treatment is carried out according to the condition of the patient, massage, healing physical education and physiotherapy are

used. The nature of the treatment is determined by the dosage and the depth of the paresis. The deeper the lesion, the longer the treatment lasts (except for active action) [8, 9, 10]. Hyperactive gymnastics affects the pattern of exercises: the bending of the participant is symmetrical in the absence of movements, damaged during passive gymnastics, muscles are weakened with general participation. The following scheme of hyperactive Gymnastics has a positive effect: active movements in the symmetrical joints with a healthy limb, passive movements of the affected limb, General active light exercises with the participation of weakened muscles.

During the period of residual complications, medical gymnastics training continues, a significant increase in the number of practical classes for training in home and professional skills, the introduction of entertainment and sports-practical elements, the formation of optimal compensation adaptations is carried out. 15-20 different massage methods are prescribed, repeating the course of treatment for 2-3 months. According to the condition, treatment is determined by orthopedic tasks (foot, hand, foot tasks, etc.) and is orthopedic, at the same time with the help of prosthetic joists (apparatus, special shoes) [11].

Currently, the presence of contracture and joint immobility is a challenge in treatment. The alternation of passive movements with active movements with massages of alternating types and undamaged areas, light thermal methods help us to restore the desired amplitude of movement. Mechanotherapy is used as secondary changes in tissues persist. Mechanical treatment is effectively used in water.

when weak paralysis or paresis develops rehabilitation measures include:

- * improving the function of the peripheral neuron;
- * prevention of muscle tissue hypotrophy;
- * prevention of contractures.

Improving nerve tissue function is achieved through the use of neurotrophic and vasoactive drugs.

To prevent severe pain and muscle hypotrophy, the following rehabilitation tools are used:

- * massage through the stimulation method (curative, dotted, linear);
- * passive and active movements in the affected organs;
- * active exercises related to muscle contraction in training (in mild conditions);
- * monitoring the process after therapeutic gymnastics;
- * electrostimulation of affected muscles.

Special attention is paid to the strengthening of proprioception in the implementation of all the important steps in the rehabilitation process. Such strengthening is mainly carried out in two ways:

- the method of resistance to dosage of the performed movement (Kabat H method - "proprioceptive neuromotor facilitation", PNF);
- use of reflexes caused by peripheral receptors.

Patients and methods

1.1. Patients

100 children aged 3 to 18 with damage to the peripheral nervous system who were being treated in the neurological rehabilitation department of the Republican Center for Rehabilitation of Children's Musculoskeletal System Diseases were taken. All children were divided into 2 groups: the main group and the control group. 26 children in the main group aged 3-7 years, 20 children under 7-11 years old, 18 children aged 11-18 years old, 15 children in the control group of children under 3-7 years old, 13 children under 7-11 years old, 11 - 8 children under 18 years of age (table 1).

Age	Hypesthesia, %		Pain caused by improper injection (antibiotic, non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs), %	
	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls

3-7 years	3.1	17.6	9.2	23.5
7-11 years	29.0	16.1	29.5	32.3
11-17 years	39.8	28.6	36.8	44.2
Average	29.5	30.9	31.3	40.9

1.2. Treatment Methods

Patients were treated with traditional medicines taking into account the dosage of the medicine depending on their age. Metabolic treatment was carried out to restore and stimulate the regeneration of nerve axons, for which neurotrophic drugs - cerebrolysin, cortexin, piracetam in an age-appropriate dose, the drug Actovegin were used, this drug also has the effect of improving reparative and venous blood circulation [12]. To improve myelination, were used group B vitamins - thiamine hydrochloride and cyanocobalamin in an age-dependent dose, as well as the oral form of the drug Nucleo CMP. To improve intersynaptic and neuro-muscular transmission, were used anticholinesterase drugs - proserin, galantamine hydrobromide, ipidacrine. Physiotherapeutic procedures include therapeutic gymnastics exercises aimed at increasing the volume of active movements, preventing the development of contractures in the joints, improving blood circulation and trophic processes in the injured limbs, eliminating trophic disorders, strengthening the regeneration of damaged nerves, and developing adaptive movements. For this purpose, passive movements were performed on the paretic limb, and the goal was to use resistance exercises to increase muscle strength. In this case, the physical loads are limited, because excessive physical activity often leads to an increase in muscle weakness in the de-activated muscles. Massage is widely used to improve blood supply and muscle trophism in cases of slow paresis [13]. We have used a general toning massage as well as a trigger point massage.

In order to prevent joint contractures, movement stiffness and deformations, overextension of paretic muscles, patients were treated by positioning them in the desired position - using plaster casts and bandages. Corsets were used in scoliosis. Neuromuscular electrostimulation was performed, stimulating electrodes were placed on the muscles taking into account the movement points. In this case, triangular electrodes were placed perpendicular to the direction of the muscle fibers, where the ends of the movement were located, the distance between the electrodes was 2-3 cm, which ensured the same excitation of all motor fibers of the stimulated muscle. Single pulses with a duration of 100-300 ms were used for marked deasabation, pulses with a duration of 1-10 ms for moderate paresis, and pulses with a duration of 0.01-0.05 ms for mild deasabation.

In order to improve neuromuscular permeability, local metabolism, to treat contractures and muscle atrophy, proserin and iodine electrophoresis are applied longitudinally to the area of damaged limbs. Current density 0.03-0.05 mA/cm², duration of effect 15-20 minutes, 10-15 treatments. Ozokerite (46-48°C) and paraffin (48-50°C) applications were applied to paretic limbs. The duration of effect is 15-25 minutes, one course includes 10-15 procedures per day.

All patients underwent reflexotherapy - electroacupuncture of biologically active points, the effect of which is aimed at improving blood circulation and muscle trophicity, increasing muscle tone and relieving pain.

In compiling the acupuncture prescription, we followed the themes of damage to the nervous system and channels related to this area from the perspective of classical acupuncture. In the presence of pain syndromes, the area of the projection of pain sensations was first influenced by the methods of inhibition, and only after that the excitatory effect was shown on the area of movement disorders. The prescription included paravertebral points and points of the posterior median canal, which have a common innervation with the damaged nerves. In the presence of serious vegetative disorders, an inhibitory effect was shown on the points of the back middle channel [14].

Complex rehabilitation work was carried out after the treatment, including general massage, increasing muscle mobility, and improving limb function. Ipigrix drug was used during complex rehabilitation.

2. Results

Of the 100 children included in the study, 64 made up the main group and 36 made up the control group (Table 2). Among patients with leg mononeuropathy, there were 30 (37.5%) cases of fibular nerve neuropathy, 13 (16.25%) cases of large calf nerve neuropathy, and 37 (46.25%) cases of small calf nerve neuropathy. The majority of patients suffering from injection (iatrogenic): 65 children (81.25%) from non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, after antibiotics - 15 (18.75%) children (diagram 1).

Diagram 1

In the main group, reflex functions in the neurological examination before and after the treatment changed noticeably (diagram 2).

Diagram 2

A treatment method was developed at the Republican Children's Rehabilitation Center, instead of the traditional 10 days in the usual hospitals, it was extended to 45 days at the Republican Children's Musculoskeletal System Rehabilitation Center. This medical approach in children's neurorehabilitation allowed to attract highly qualified specialists in order to improve the full scope of

rehabilitation activities in the shortest possible time for children, and the level of children's disability was reduced.

2.1. Improvement of treatment group after 45 day complex rehabilitation

Achilles reflex ranged from 0.0% to $80.4 \pm 8.2\%$ in the main group and $56.7\% \pm 5.1\%$ in the control group ($r \leq 0.05$). Joint-muscle tenderness in the main group increased by $57.8 \pm 7.1\%$, compared to $24.5 \pm 3.7\%$ in the control group. These indicators are explained by the complete or partial restoration of afferent pathways under the influence of physical rehabilitation. As a result, the degree of dependence on the walking level from the groups leading children decreased from $23.5 \pm 4.6\%$ in the main group to $4.2 \pm 1.7\%$, and in the comparison group to $6.7 \pm 2.1\%$ ($r \leq 0.05$) (diagram 3).

After rehabilitation measures in the main group, the rate of symptoms of neuropathy due to incorrect injections was $46.8 \pm 7.4\%$, compared to $23.5 \pm 2.6\%$ in the control group, neuropathy of the feet was $37.8\% \pm 3.0$. 56% of three year old children ($r < 0.05$) had foot measurements of 57.6 ± 1.5 cm (hypotrophy) and 51.8 ± 1.6 cm (atrophy) in 44% of children, before rehabilitation in children under 5 years of age The length of the legs of 63% of children was 65.4 ± 1.7 cm, ($r < 0.05$) (hypotrophy and 37% of children were found to be 61.3 ± 1.4 cm (atrophy). Before rehabilitation, 58% of 7 year old children had a leg length of 70.5 ± 1.6 cm (hypotrophy), and 42% of children had a leg length of 68.4 ± 1.4 cm (atrophy). Almost all children (96%) observed improvements after a set of rehabilitation processes in the main group. Thus, in 3-year-old children, the average age of the legs increased by 2.4 ± 0.2 cm, and in 90% of children of this age, the leg length was 59.8 ± 1.2 cm, while in 10% of children, the leg length decreased and the leg length was 58, It was 6 ± 1.1 cm ($r < 0.05$). It was found that only 71% of children improved in the comparison group where the traditional rehabilitation method was used. Therefore, in the comparison group, the leg length increased slightly and in 3-year-old children it was 58.2 ± 0.8 cm, and in the 5-year-old children in the main group, the leg length increased by an average of 3.7 ± 0.1 cm ($r < 0.05$). In 8% of children, the leg length increased slightly and was 67.8 ± 1.3 cm, among children under 5 years of age, 68% of children in the control group improved their condition. The length of the legs partially increased to 66.5 ± 1.5 cm, while 32% did not change the length of the legs, which indicates the presence of hypotrophy or atrophy in the legs. In 7 year old children in the main group, the leg length increased by an average of 2.8 ± 0.2 cm ($r < 0.05$). There was little change in the comparison group. Thus, among the examined 7 year old children, the leg length increased by 71.6 ± 0.4 cm in 64% ($r < 0.05$). Positive changes were not detected in 36% of children in the comparison group. Leg length indicators before treatment and after treatment in the main group of children aged 3-7 years were noticeably (diagram 4).

Diagram 4

3. Discussion

After complete rehabilitation of patients in the main group, a complete decrease in acute pain syndrome was noted, average pain decreased by 78.9%, constant by 92.6%, periodic by 75%.

In addition, there are different approaches to the examination and interpretation of the obtained clinical data among different specialists who are faced with this problem: among pediatricians, neuropathologists, rehabilitologists, surgeons, etc. The impact of harmful factors is important in the concept of formation of postinjection neuropathies. Quantitative risk indicators were used to assess health and the basis of preventive measures, as well as epidemiological analysis of the relationship of the disease with the age of the child [15].

Determining the cause and effect relationships of disease development, creating prognostic models is an urgent task of pediatric neurology. Despite the improvement of existing risk assessment methods, there is no unified methodology in our country.

At the same time the modern principles of medical rehabilitation of children with neuromotor system damage should include comprehensive, continuous, step-by-step, individual implementation, therapeutic physical exercises, physiotherapy, pharmacotherapy, orthopedic procedures, orthopedic care, timely provision of orthopedic equipment [16]. In order to improve the quality indicators, increase the quality of life, and reduce the expenses of the patients' relatives during the implementation of complex rehabilitation measures, the Ipiatrix drug was used, and its most effective results were reflected in the recovery of the patient's movements and the increase in muscle strength.

4. Conclusion

5. The data obtained during the study confirmed the therapeutic value of the practical application of the rehabilitation treatment developed by us for postinjection mononeuropathy of the legs in children. The use of the rehabilitation method developed by us in practical medicine (45 days), the use of the drug Ipiatrix in this process allows to significantly improve the clinical course of post-injection mononeuropathy, as well as to restore the child's physical activity, which leads to an improvement in the quality of life.

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Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

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Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
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